

Complexes of Ag^I, Tl^I, Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Ru^{II}, Pd^{II}, Rh^{III}, Ru^{III} and Ir^{III} with 4-salicylideneamino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazin(4H)-5-one

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The complexes of Ag^I, Tl^I, Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Ru^{II}, Pd^{II}, Rh^{III}, Ru^{III} and Ir^{III} with 4-salicylideneamino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazin(4H)-5-one (SAMT) have been synthesised. Octahedral structures have been proposed for the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Ru^{II}, Ru^{III}, Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} complexes, square-planar for the Pd^{II} complex, tetrahedral for the Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} complexes and linear polymeric structures for the Tl^I and Ag^I complexes. The ligand coordinates to the metal ions through thiol sulfur after deprotonation and with azomethine nitrogen. Phenolic oxygen of the ligand is also involved in bonding after deprotonation in few of the complexes.

The importance of Schiff base ligands and their complexes with transition metals have enhanced especially due to their biological applications. Metal chelates of certain multidentate Schiff bases have been used for the purification of metals because of their high volatility and solubility in non-polar solvents¹. The metal complexes with Schiff bases find various industrial and biological applications. The present paper discusses the synthesis and characterization of the complexes of Ag^I, Tl^I, Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ru^{II}, Rh^{III}, Ru^{III} and Ir^{III} with 4-salicylideneamino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazin(4H)-5-one (SAMT).

Fig. 1

Results and Discussion

The analytical results (Table 1) show that Ag^I and Tl^I form ML type complexes while Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II} and Pd^{II} form ML₂ type complexes with SAMT. The Pd^{II} complex contain a molecule of water and is of ML type. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Ru^{II} complexes contain three molecules of water coordinated to the metal. The presence of coordinated water molecules in the Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Pd^{II} and Ru^{II} complexes were further confirmed by TGA and spectral data. The Ru^{III}, Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} complexes are of ML₂ type.

The magnetic susceptibility studies show that all the complexes, excepting that of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Ru^{III} are diamagnetic.

Nickel(II) complexes in octahedral field contain two unpaired electrons and hence shows paramagnetism. Their magnetic moment are in general slightly higher than the spin-only value of 2.83 B.M. This difference may be due to either the ferromagnetic interaction in the clusters² or to

Jahn-Teller distortion or both. The magnetic moments of the Ni^{II} complex (3.11 B.M.) is in good agreement with those reported for octahedral nickel(II) complexes^{2,3}. The reason for the higher observed value than the expected one may be due to the supraposed reasons. Since the T_d symmetry which gives triplet state as the ground state, the orbital contributions would have been much more^{3,4} than that are actually observed. A distorted O_h symmetry for the Ni^{II} complexes seems to be more plausible than symmetry. However, further support to this view comes from spectral data.

The Co^{II} has a d⁷ system and its complexes show paramagnetism either equivalent to three unpaired electrons (octahedral or tetrahedral) or equivalent to one unpaired electron (square-planar). The magnetic moment of the complex is 4.72 B.M. Since the orbital contribution of tetrahedral Co^{II} is much less than that of octahedral complexes, tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes have generally lower values of magnetic moments as compared to that of octahedral complexes⁵. This high degree of orbital contribution for octahedral complexes is due to the three-fold degeneracy of ⁴T_{1g} ground state. The value of magnetic moment of Co^{II}-SAMT complex lies well within the range of high-spin octahedral complexes^{3,4}.

The magnetic moment of the Ru^{III} complex is 1.91 B.M. The normal value of magnetic moment for a Ru^{III} complex is 2.10 B.M.⁶ at room temperature. The low value may be due to low symmetry ligand fields, metal-metal interactions and extended overlap of the metal-ligands^{6,7}. The magnetic moments of the complexes with ²T_{2g} ground term are lowered due to progressive quenching of the orbital angular momentum by spin-orbital coupling which removes the degeneracy of the triplet ground term. Extensive spin-orbit coupling can also reduce the magnetic moment below that of the spin-only value.

Table 1. Analytical data of SAMT complexes

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
	C	H	N	S	M
[Ag(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S)]	33.80 (33.81)	1.96 (1.97)	15.76 (15.78)	9.04 (9.02)	30.42 (30.40)
[Tl(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S)]	26.60 (26.59)	1.56 (1.55)	12.43 (12.41)	7.07 (7.09)	45.25 (45.28)
[Cd(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂]	39.59 (39.58)	2.32 (2.31)	18.46 (18.47)	10.57 (10.55)	18.53 (18.54)
[Zn(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂]	42.91 (42.90)	2.51 (2.50)	20.01 (20.02)	11.46 (11.44)	11.70 (11.70)
[Pb(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂]	34.25 (34.23)	2.01 (2.00)	15.95 (15.97)	9.15 (9.13)	29.57 (29.55)
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S).3H ₂ O]	33.44 (33.43)	3.34 (3.34)	15.61 (15.60)	8.93 (8.92)	16.44 (16.42)
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S).3H ₂ O]	33.47 (33.46)	3.36 (3.35)	15.62 (15.61)	8.99 (8.92)	16.35 (16.42)
[Ru(C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S).3H ₂ O]	29.90 (29.92)	2.98 (2.99)	13.95 (13.96)	8.99 (7.98)	25.22 (25.20)
[Pd(C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S).H ₂ O]	32.41 (32.40)	2.17 (2.16)	15.13 (15.12)	8.65 (8.64)	28.74 (28.73)
[Ru(C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S)- (C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S)]	40.42 (40.40)	2.18 (2.19)	18.87 (18.86)	10.75 (10.77)	17.03 (17.01)
[Rh(C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S)- (C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S)]	40.26 (40.27)	2.17 (2.18)	18.80 (18.79)	10.75 (10.74)	17.26 (17.27)
[Ir(C ₁₀ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S)- (C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S)]	35.04 (35.03)	1.91 (1.90)	16.36 (16.35)	9.35 (9.34)	28.04 (28.05)

Thermogravimetric analysis of the complexes of SAMT indicates the presence of water molecules in the Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Ru^{II} complexes. The loss in weight of these complexes occurs in the temperature range 90–225°, which indicates the loss of coordinated water molecules. The thermogram of Ni^{II}-SAMT complex indicates a loss in weight of around 17.5%, which corresponds to the loss of three water molecules, when heated from 90 to 225°. A steep decrease in weight is observed in the thermograms of the complexes at a temperature range 250–550°. This may be attributed to the oxidation of the organic matter and formation of the metal oxides. All the other complexes are stable upto 200° and decompose in two major steps. The final products at 600–800° are mainly metal oxides.

The molar conductance values of all the complexes are in the range 2.5–30.8 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm². The comparatively low values indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytes and are neutral in nature.

Electronic spectral band positions and assignments in respect of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} complexes of SAMT are given below.

For high spin octahedral complexes of Co^{II}, three transitions are expected in the electronic spectra at ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ in the order of increasing energies. The first transition was not recorded but its position was calculated from the second

transition. The values of the crystal field stabilization energy (10 *Dq*), Racah parameter (*B*) and the covalency factor (β) have been evaluated⁸.

In the case of six-coordinate octahedral and pseudo-octahedral nickel(II) complexes, the three spin-allowed transitions from ${}^3A_{2g}(F)$ to ${}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(P)$ generally full within the range 7000–13000, 11000–20000 and 19000–27000 respectively⁸. The ratio of the frequencies of the second to the first transition would be around 1.8 (Refs. 4, 9). The first transition corresponding to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ is not recorded in the electronic spectra. The assignment of the transition and ligand field parameters are calculated and presented. The calculated *B* values are lower than the free-ion value of 1080 cm⁻¹.

This metal ion, which generally forms square-planar complexes has *D*_{4h} symmetry of the ligand field around the central metal ion². The metal orbitals, namely, *s*, *p* and *d*, span (i) *a*_{1g}, (ii) *e*_u and *a*_{2u} and (iii) *b*_{1g}, *b*_{2g}, *a*_{1g} and *e*_g representations respectively. Similarly, the ligand orbitals transform as *b*_{1g}, *a*_{1g} and *e*_u. The sigma bond formation between the metal ion and the ligand units would use one *d*-orbital (*b*_{1g}), one *s*-orbital (*a*_{1g}) and two *p*-orbital (*e*_u) of the metal ion. The ground state for the low spin *d*⁸ system is therefore ${}^1A_{1g}$. Assuming *D*_{4h} symmetry of the field around the central metal ion, one should expect three spin-allowed and three spin-forbidden bands in the electronic spectra of the complexes¹⁰ corresponding to the transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{1g}$. However, not all the possible transitions can really be observed because some of them are masked either due to charge transfer or due to inter-ligand interactions.

The ground state of Ru^{III} is ${}^2T_{2g}$ and the first excited doublet levels in the order of increasing energy are ${}^2A_{2g}$ and ${}^2T_{1g}$ which arise from ${}^1T_{2g}$, *e*_g configuration¹¹. According to Tanabe and Sugano, eight transitions are possible from the ground state (*t*_{2g}⁵) to the doublet state of the (*t*_{2g}⁴, *e*_g) configuration for octahedral Ru^{III} complexes and two spin-forbidden transitions from the ground state to the (*t*_{2g}⁴, *e*_g) quartet states¹³. Three transitions are observed in the complex of Ru^{III}, the first two bands are assigned to the ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transitions and the third one to ${}^2A_{2g}$, ${}^2T_{1g}$ levels respectively. The 10 *Dq* and *B* values calculated using the literature data, viz. ${}^2T_{2g}$ (*t*_{2g}⁵) = 0, ${}^4T_{1g}$ (*t*_{2g}⁴, *e*_g) = 10 *Dq* - 5*B* - 4*C*, ${}^4T_{1g}$ (*t*_{2g}⁴, *e*_g) = 10 *Dq* + 3*B* - 4*C* and ${}^2A_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g}$ (*t*_{2g}⁴, *e*_g) = 10 *Dq* - 2*B* - *C*, are in conformity with that of other Ru^{III} complexes with similar donors.

The ground state of the metal ions Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} in an octahedral field is ${}^1A_{1g}$. The excited states corresponding to *t*_{2g}⁵, *e*_g configuration are ${}^3T_{1g}$, ${}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{2g}$ in the increasing order of energy. Thus four transitions can be expected as ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$. The values of 10 *Dq*, *B* and β evaluated using the

following equations : ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g} = 10 Dq - C$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g} = 10 Dq + 16B - C$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} = 10 Dq - 3C$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} = 10 Dq + 8B - 3C$, are in conformity with that of other Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} complexes with similar donors.

The infrared spectrum of the ligand has bands at 3100–3000 (NH) and 2900 cm⁻¹ (C–H). The band at 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O) of the ligand is also observed in the spectra of the complexes (Table 2). This shows the non-participation of the carbonyl group in bonding. The ligand bands at 1630 and 1590 cm⁻¹ is assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$ of the azomethine linkage^{12,13}. The slight shift of the band to lower wavenumber side in the complexes indicates the coordination of the nitrogen with the metal ions.

Table 2. Ir bands (cm⁻¹) of SAMT and its complexes

Ligand	Tl ^I , Ag ^I , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} complexes	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Rh ^{II} , Pd ^{II} complexes	Ir ^{III} , Rh ^{III} Ru ^{III} complexes	Assignment
–	–	3500	–	ν _{OH} water
3100–3000	2980 ± 10	2970 ± 5	2910 ± 10	ν _{NH}
2900	2880 ± 10	2880 ± 10	2890 ± 5	ν _{C-H}
1670	1675 ± 5	1650 ± 5	1670 ± 10	ν _{C=O}
1630	1610 ± 5	1600	1610 ± 10	ν _{C=N}
1550	1545	1540 ± 5	1540 ± 10	Thioamide band I
1420	1460 ± 5	1470	1470 ± 5	Thioamide band II
1310	1310 ± 5	1350	1350 ± 5	ν _{C-O}
1190	1190 ± 10	1200 ± 10	1200 ± 10	Thioamide band III
1050	1050 ± 10	1050 ± 5	1050 ± 10	ν _{N-N} triazinering
–	–	890 ± 10	–	Characteristic of coordinated water
760	710 ± 5	710 ± 5	705 ± 10	Thioamide band IV and Ph. gp. with 5 adj. H-atoms
680	680 ± 5	680 ± 5	680 ± 5	Aromatic ring
–	470 ± 10	460 ± 10	460 ± 10	ν _{M-N}
–	–	450 ± 5	450 ± 10	ν _{M-O}
–	330 ± 10	320 ± 10	400 ± 10	ν _{M-S}

The ligand molecule containing thioamide moiety is expected to exist in tautomeric thiol and thione forms (Fig. 1). Due to the presence of thioamide moiety, four characteristic thioamide bands can be expected in the spectra of the ligands. The position of the thioamide band I (1530–1560 cm⁻¹) in the spectrum of the ligand is not shifted appreciably in the spectra of the complexes. But the position of thioamide band II of the ligand (1420 cm⁻¹) suffered a considerable shift towards higher wavenumber side in the complexes (1460–70 cm⁻¹). The ligand band at 1290–1320 cm⁻¹ (C–O)¹⁴ shifted to higher wavenumber side in some complexes, indicating coordination through oxygen of the phenolic group, while in some complexes this shift was not observed and hence the phenolic oxygen is not involved in bonding. The thioamide band IV (760–790 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the ligand is shifted to lower wavenumber side in their complexes¹⁵. The increased intensity of the thioamide

band IV in the spectra of the ligands may be due to the mixing of thioamide band IV and the band characteristic of phenyl ring. In the complexes the band around 790 cm⁻¹ is due to the presence of phenyl group. The band around 690 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring) is observed in the spectra of the ligand and the complexes.

New bands are also observed in the spectra of the complexes due to ν_{M-N} , ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-S} coupled with other modes of vibrations of the ligand molecules. Bands due to coordinated water are also observed in the spectra of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pd^{II} and Ru^{II} complexes around 3500 and 890 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} and characteristics of coordinated water molecules respectively.

On the basis of the above results octahedral structures have been proposed for the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Ru^{II}, Ru^{III}, Rh^{III} and Ir^{III} complexes, square-planar for the Pd^{II} complex, tetrahedral for the Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} complexes and linear polymeric structures for the Tl^I and Ag^I complexes. The ligand molecules coordinate to the metal ions through thiol sulfur after deprotonation and with azomethine nitrogen. Phenolic oxygen of SAMT is also involved in bonding after deprotonation in few of the complexes (Pb^{II}, Ru^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Ru^{III}, Rh^{III} and Ir^{III}).

Experimental

The chemicals used were all of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. The ligand was synthesized¹⁶ by condensing 4-amino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazin(4H)-5-one with salicylaldehyde. The product was recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 148–149° and characterized by physical methods. The complexes were prepared by refluxing the respective metal chlorides/nitrates/acetates (0.01 mol) and the ligand (0.02 mol) in ethanol (75 ml) for 2–3 h. The separated solid was washed with hot water, warm ethanol and ether and dried at 110–130°.

Sulfur and the metal contents were determined by the standard methods. C, H and N were analyzed at R.S.I.C. of Punjab University. The magnetic susceptibility was determined with a Gouy balance at room temperature. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Mettler TA 4000 thermal analyzer by heating the complexes in air at a rate of 10° / min upto 800° at Department of Chemical Engineering, KREC, Suratkal. The molar conductivity of the complexes (in 1 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ DMF solution) was measured using an Elico conductivity meter. Absorption spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer and infrared spectra (KBr/CsI) on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer.

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